

**Proceedings of the 31st International Congress and Exhibition on
Condition Monitoring and Diagnostic Engineering Management**

2-5 July 2018

Sun City, Rustenburg, South Africa

Editors

P.S. Heyns, P.A. van Vuuren, G. van Schoor, R.B.K.N. Rao

Investigations on Augmented Reality based maintenance practices within SMEs

M. Müller^{1,2}, D. Stegelmeyer², R. Mishra¹

¹ School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom

² Institut für Interdisziplinäre Technik, Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany

ABSTRACT

Maintenance services provided by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) play a fundamental role in industrial asset management. The vast majority of OEMs provide maintenance services to their customers, as most customers now outsource complex maintenance tasks. For many OEMs the economic value of operations has even shifted from manufacturing traditional products, to providing services required to operate and maintain their installed base. In general downtime is expensive and maintenance activities are often conducted under time pressure. However, maintenance processes are knowledge intensive and field service technicians have to cope with increasingly complex and diverse systems. To stand out from competitors and to satisfy customer needs, productivity improvement in maintenance processes is urgently required. Augmented Reality (AR) technologies, e.g. head mounted displays (HMD) can assist field service technicians in improving efficiency of maintenance operations. Systems for mobile collaborative AR supported maintenance are commercially available, and the benefits of AR supported maintenance work are generally evident. Still, on a wider scale in the industrial maintenance service delivery, the technology is far from established. From the perspective of small and medium-sized enterprises (SME), with a limited number of field service technicians, remote support for customers and service partners might be an opportunity to enhance resources availability. This study investigates ten business cases of mobile collaborative AR systems using HMDs for services delivery. The research strategy follows an exploratory approach. Based on focus group discussions with representatives of SMEs and semi-structured interviews with industry experts, enablers and barriers for the use of mobile collaborative AR systems are determined.

Keywords: augmented reality, head mounted displays, industrial asset management, maintenance, servitization

Corresponding author: Maike Müller (maike.mueller@hud.ac.uk)

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, traditional manufacturing companies of different kinds of capital goods have moved up the value chain and become service or solution based businesses in order to distinguish themselves from their competitors, better meet customer's needs, and thus survive in increasingly competitive product markets [1–5]. For many OEMs, regardless of their position in the supply chain, the economic value has shifted from manufacturing traditional products, to providing services required to operate and maintain their installed base [3][6]. The vast majority of capital goods manufacturers provides at least basic services, such as spare parts supply or repair and maintenance-on-demand [6]. In general downtime is expensive and maintenance activities are often conducted under time pressure. Besides, customers often expect availability commitments for specialised service technicians for recurring maintenance activities as well as in cases of unscheduled downtime. Maintenance processes, however, are knowledge intensive and maintenance personnel have to cope with increasingly complex and diverse systems [7]. To stand out from competitors and satisfy customer needs, productivity improvement in maintenance processes is required. With respect to their limited resources and difficulties to implement service-oriented strategies, SMEs are challenged in particular [8][9]. Nevertheless, SMEs are an important part of most economies. In Germany, for instance, 85 % of machinery and equipment industries are SMEs. They account for nearly 30 % of the total turnover generated and 37 % of the people employed by the sector as a whole [10].

One concept, to address aforementioned challenges and increasingly complex maintenance operations, is the real-time collaboration between experts and on-site field service technicians via mobile collaborative AR systems using HMDs [11][12]. Generally, remote expert assistance produces quicker and more accurate troubleshooting and repairs [13] and is one of the most popular application areas for HMDs [14]. For SMEs, considering their limited resources, mobile collaborative AR might be an opportunity to increase customer satisfaction, withstand competitive pressure, and broaden their sales network [15]. But even though AR and HMDs have been a research interest for more than 50 years [16], there are very few concrete examples of implementation in industry and if implemented, most applications are on a field test level in large enterprises (LE) [17][18]. In the past, researchers developed prototypical systems for mobile collaborative AR and tested those systems in experiments or case studies [11][12][15][19][20]. Those systems usually include a wearable computing system (e.g. HMD) worn by a technician and a user interface to enable collaborative communication between remote experts and technicians in the field. The main function of the HMD is to capture a live audio and video stream [11]. The user interface displays the live stream captured by the HMD's camera and features communication and documentation functionality, e.g. video recording, screenshots, document sharing, chat, language translation and laser pointing into the live stream. HMDs used can be either see-through HMDs or video display HMDs (non-see-through). See-through HMDs are based on waveguides, semi-transparent monocular or binocular mirrors that reflect computer generated images to augment the real world (e.g. Epson BT-350, Google Glass, Microsoft HoloLens). Non-see-through HMDs capture the real world, overlay the computer-generated information and display the composited image in a small monitor placed in front of one of the user's eyes (e.g. RealWear HMT-1, Vuzix M300) [18]. Mobile collaborative AR systems, both hardware and user interfaces (e.g. web-based communication platforms), are commercially available. However, on a broad scale in industrial maintenance service delivery, the technology is far from established. Only 3.4 % of companies currently use HMDs in the manufacturing context [14]. Previous work on mobile collaborative AR has mostly been focused on the development of systems and aspects of usability of features [21][22], whereas now that the technology seems to be capable of handling complex tasks, our focus is on service business cases enabled through the technology.

In particular, we would like to explore barriers and enablers for the use of mobile collaborative AR systems supporting services provided by small and medium-sized machinery manufacturers (OEMs) on their installed base. Even though we investigate OEMs that offer diverse products, the service delivery is characterised by some similarities: Those similarities are: a multi-variant technically complex installed base, customers that typically outsource complex maintenance tasks and often expect availability commitments. Especially, availability commitments for specialised service technicians are a major concern for SMEs. In this paper we solely take the perspective of the OEM providing paid services for their installed base. Therefore, the term maintenance describes service offerings, the OEM charges for. We do not take the perspective of the customer and/or their maintenance function.

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

Given the comparative lack of existing literature on the business perspective of mobile collaborative AR, especially on barriers and enablers, we aim to explore business cases, barriers and enablers for the use of the technology in service delivery. In order to address the aforementioned research aim, a qualitative research approach with a strong exploratory notion has been used. This approach was selected on conceptual grounds rather than for its representativeness [23].

Data was collected in two focus group discussions and individual semi-structured interviews with 20 representatives from 17 German companies (table 1). The companies used in our sample were classified following the definition of the Institut für Mittelstandsforschung [24]. According to this definition SMEs are the companies that employ less than 500 people. The sample consists of 14 machinery manufacturers, referred to as OEMs, of which ten are SMEs and four are LEs. Focus group participants and interviewees all held positions of strategic responsibility for the service business to ensure validity of results. In Addition to the OEM perspective, representatives of two HMD manufacturers and a system integrator, referred to as industry experts, are also part of the sample to broaden the perspective and provided additional insights. The industry experts provide insight from their experience of many AR implementation projects in capital goods industries. Additionally, 24 use cases of AR supported service delivery found in non-academic publications on the internet were analysed and compared to the findings derived from the empirical data (table 2). This aimed to fill the above mentioned lack of academic literature.

Table 1: Sample of the interview study

Position of Interviewees	Company / Industry	Company Size	Company Type	Interview Method
General Manager 1 General Manager 2	Air Cleaning Plant Technology	SME	OEM	Focus Group and Individual Interview
Head of Service Sales & Repair	Coating Equipment	LE	OEM	Focus Group
Manager After Sales 1 Manager After Sales 2	Control and Regulation Systems	LE	OEM	Focus Group
Head of Customer Support	Food Processing Plant Engineering	LE	OEM	Focus Group
CEO	HMD Hardware/Software System Integrator	SME	HMD provider / industry expert	Focus Group and Individual Interview
Business Development Manager	HMD Manufacturer	SME	HMD provider / industry expert	Focus Group Individual Interview
Business Development Director	HMD Manufacturer & Software Provider	SME	HMD provider / industry expert	Focus Group and Individual Interview
Innovation Manager	Machine Tools	LE	OEM	Focus Group
CEO	Machine Tools	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Head of Customer Support Service Engineer	Machine Tools	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Quality and Process Management Engineer	Machine Tools	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Service Manager	Machine Tools	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Director of Service and Quality Management	Machine Tools	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Head of Mechanical Engineering	Plastics Processing Machinery	SME	OEM	Focus Group
Head of Customer Support	Power Plant Engineering	SME	OEM	Focus Group
CEO	Steam Generator Technology	SME	OEM	Individual Interview
Sales Director	Wastewater Technology	SME	OEM	Focus Group

The focus group discussions took place in December 2017 and January 2018. We selected companies that intended to use HMDs for their service delivery in the near future and do not compete in the same markets. The absence of completion was important to ensure that participants share their views openly. However, the experience of focus group participants with the technology varied. Some companies tested HMDs in the past, while other participants had no experience with HMDs. This limited experience was addressed within a half-day workshop on features of the technology prior to the discussion. In addition to the focus group discussions, five semi-structured interviews with industry experts and companies that already tested HMDs within their service operation were conducted. These interviews aimed to gain a deeper understanding of business cases, enablers and barriers previously discussed in the focus groups (table 1). The interviews were conducted between February and March 2018 via telephone and lasted between 60 and 120 minutes. Data collected from focus groups and interviews were recorded and transcribed for analysis. The empirical data was analysed by applying thematic coding according to Miles et al. (2014) using NVivo 11 [25].

Table 2: Analysed internet use cases of AR systems

No.	Use Case	Main features of AR system	No.	Use Case	Main features of AR system
# 1	Bosch Automotive	Unidirectional AR assembly instruction, contextual data provision, access to knowledge data base	# 13	MA micro automation	MCAR-system
# 2	Bosch Rexroth	MCAR-system	# 14	MAN Truck & Bus	Unidirectional AR assembly/repair instructions, 3D-tutorial training, contextual data provision
# 3	Caterpillar	MCAR-system	# 15	Mekorot	Unidirectional AR assembly instruction, MCAR-system
# 4	Daikin Netherlands	MCAR-system, access to knowledge data base and error codes	# 16	NORDEN	MCAR-system
# 5	GE Aviation	AR assembly/repair instructions with feedback on performance of task, video tutorials, MCAR-system	# 17	Porsche	MCAR-system
# 6	Gebhardt Fördertechnik	MCAR-system	# 18	Schmidt & Heinzmann	MCAR-system, overlay of process data
# 7	Getinge	Unidirectional AR training	# 19	Schulz Systemtechnik	Unidirectional AR assembly instruction, overlay of process data
# 8	Koenig & Bauer	MCAR-system, access to knowledge data base (projected)	# 20	Systronik	AR-based measure monitoring
# 9	Kieback & Peter	MCAR-system	# 21	TGW Lifetime	MCAR-system
# 10	Kurtz	MCAR-system	# 22	Thyssenkrupp	Unidirectional AR projection of 3D-models of products (pre-sales), MCAR-system
# 11	Lee Company	MCAR-system	# 23	VMT - Tunnelbau	MCAR-system
# 12	Leybold	Unidirectional AR assembly instruction, contextual data provision	# 24	Wärtsilä	MCAR-system, overlay of process data

MCAR-system = mobile callaboration AR-system

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following section presents the results of our investigation and compares the findings of present work to earlier works. First, ten business cases for the technology are presented. Thereafter, enablers and barriers for the use of the technology, which we derived from the two focus group discussions, the five interviews and the supporting 24 use cases, are discussed.

Our research identified ten business cases listed in table 3. Besides supporting their own service technicians with mobile collaboration AR systems, SMEs also intend to equip service partners, sub-contractors and customer’s personnel. Inspection, diagnosis and repair, assembly/installation, and training are the main service operations companies propose to support with the use of HMDs. Our findings correspond with Palmarini et al. (2018) who analysed 30 academic articles on the state of the art of AR in maintenance and found that dis/assembly (33%), repair (26%), inspection/diagnosis (26%) and training (15%) were the maintenance operations described in those articles [18]. In addition, we learned that application support to improve customer production processes was identified as a valuable business case for mobile collaborative AR systems. Application issues usually occur sporadically. Thus, the remote approach enables the application engineer to support customers in the moment of occurrence.

In correspondence with Quint et al. (2017), the use cases analysed (table 2) are confirmed to be demonstrators or test level systems of predominately LEs [17]. Therefore, those use cases provided little information on organizational barriers of the implementation of mobile collaborative AR systems from the perspective of SMEs. Nonetheless, the use cases analysed did confirm the interest of companies in mobile collaborative AR systems as 18 out of 24 feature this functionality. Other functionalities found in the use cases were unidirectional AR application supporting step-by-step instructions and training scenarios that aim to reduce errors and minimize training effort.

Table 3: Business cases and value of mobile collaborative AR systems for service delivery

Business Case	No.	Description	Value for SMEs	Discussed in focus group
Inspection, diagnosis and repair	# 1	OEM's service technicians are equipped with HMDs and are remotely supported by a specialist.	Time saving for diagnosis/repairs/identification of needed spare parts, spontaneous involvement of further specialists, new technicians are faster able to work independently, automatic video/screenshot documentation in session protocols	both
	# 2	Service technicians of service partners and sub-contractors are equipped with HMD and are remotely supported by an OEM's specialist.	Reduction of traveling time and expenses, increase of partners service quality though remote OEM back up, consistent service portfolio also for distant customers	both
	# 3	Customer's maintenance personnel is equipped with HMD and is remotely supported by a OME's specialist.	Reduction of traveling time and expenses, avoidance of unnecessary technician deployment, briefer respond time to service inquiries (increase of service quality through ad hoc support if no spare parts are needed), precise spare part identification	both
Training	# 4	Customer's operators are equipped with HMDs and are remotely instructed by a OEM's trainer, e.g. in case of frequent fluctuation.	Resource saving for operator on-site trainings, better training results compared to showroom trainings (actions have been really executed by operator and not only simulated by trainer, session video can be recalled by customer operators)	both
	# 5	Service technicians of service partners and sub-contractors are equipped with HMDs and are remotely instructed by a OEM's trainer.	Increase of service quality (better skilled technicians), reduction of training cost could lead to more frequent trainings, increase of customer loyalty through international quality service, less "firefighting" through headquarter	one
	# 6	Service personnel of subsidiaries are equipped with HMDs and are remotely instructed by a OEM's trainer.	Time and cost savings for trainer travels, more frequent training through decreased time and costs, increase of international service quality, less "firefighting" through headquarter	both
System installation	# 7	OEM's service technician is equipped with HMD and is supported by OEM's or component supplier's specialist, e.g. software engineers or design engineers.	Relaxation of human resources situation (saving specialist travels), spontaneous involvement of further specialists, installation condition documented immediately (as is versus as engineered)	one
System acceptance tests	# 8	OEM's service technicians is equipped with HMD and remotely supported in the process of system acceptance.	Saving specialist travels, spontaneous involvement of further specialists, video documentation of performance approval according to sales contract	one
	# 9	Pre-delivery acceptance test of sub-supplier's components. OEMs technicians is equipped with the HMD and components are remotely accepted by the sub-supplier.	Faster delivery of system to end customer, decrease of cost for acceptance tests (sub-suppliers traveling expenses)	one
Application support	# 10	OEMs remote application specialist collaboratively optimises customer's production process, while customer's operator is equipped with HMD and executes instructions on-site.	Specialist support in the moment of occurrence (application issues often occur sporadic), saving specialist travels	one

3.1. Enablers and Opportunities

Improvement of OEM service delivery (Business cases #1, #4, #7, #8, #10, table 3)

Companies expect that hands-free collaboration and “seeing through the users’ eye” will lead to productivity improvement in service delivery. If the problem can't be solved immediately, at least errors occurred and spare parts needed can be identified more quickly and more precisely. The mobile collaborative AR approach is superior compared to today’s hotline support in combination with emailed photos or videos. The findings can be compared

to Fussell et al. (2003), who found that technology enabled shared visual spaces are superior compared to audio only collaboration [26]. The latest generation of HMDs seem to be mature enough to provide those shared visual spaces. Equipping technicians with HMDs also enables companies to deploy them to customers with less training, as they are covered by remote specialists. „*With the glasses [mobile collaborative AR system] new field service technicians don't have to be deployed alongside an experienced technician as a 'second man' for such a long time to become familiar with our diverse systems.*” Predictably initial training is one of the most popular application areas for HMDs [14].

Reduction of service costs for OEM (Business cases #1, #2, #7, #8, #9)

Cost reduction, unsurprisingly, is an enabler of mobile collaborative AR. Cost reduction primarily derives from the reduction of traveling time and expenses for deploying field service technicians, trainers, and specialists. In SMEs the company's specialised know-how is often concentrated in few people. A general manager of an SME stated: “[...] *we can multiply our experience without going on an airplane. This is really valuable to us.*” Mourtzis et al. (2017) presents a case of a robotics SME that could lower costs from 1.370 € to 150 € for a battery replacement, a problem which can also be solved by instructing the customer's workers remotely, instead of deploying an OEM's technician to the customer's production site [15]. Especially during the warranty period of products, field service technician deployment is aimed to be avoided, as cost can't be charged. If the first error detection process can be conducted remotely, the value obtained is twofold. First, unnecessary technician deployment can be diminished, which reduces costs. A statement of a focus group participant illustrates the problem: “[...] *It happens that someone needs to go to Poland [from Germany] and then he takes two wires, reconnects them and drives back home. For this purpose the glasses are perfect. [...]*”. Second, service enquiries can be responded to faster, which may avoid contractual penalties. “*Particularly the immediate [response is valuable to us]. I really can't tell the customer, 'it is a warranty case, so I will have time for you only next week'.*”

Ability to respond to service enquiry (Business cases #2, #4, #10)

Specialised field service technicians are hardly available on labour markets. Equipping customers with HMDs enables ad hoc problem solving and minimises the effects of the human resource shortage. Deploying technicians to customer's sites for minor problem solving leads to serious problems for SMEs. With their limited number of field service technicians, the use of mobile collaborative AR systems can ensure the ability to respond to customer errors in case of simultaneous service enquiries. As one manager puts it “*We are a relatively small company and we have a major problem with capacity. We can't recruit 200 percent technicians, because there is no one available. [...]* For me it is not so much about money, but about being able to respond at all.”

International consistent quality of service (Business cases #2, #3, #4, #5, #6, #10)

During the discussion the participants stressed that generally, domestic service is of higher quality than service to distant customers. The use of mobile collaborative AR systems also enables SMEs to provide their customers with an international service network. Equipping subcontractors, service partners and customers with HMDs supports quality standards. “*On the one hand, I train the employees [of the service partner], on the other hand we enable them to provide services to the customers which they can't provide today. Because they are just not capable to provide these services. Besides, the training can be performed while he [the service partner's technician] is having the problem at the end customer's site.*” The qualification of service partners is important because SMEs are generally more reliant on a broader partner network to perform their field services [27] than LEs with subsidiaries in major markets. Above that, the reduction of training costs is expected to lead to more frequent training of subsidiaries, service partners and customer's operators. This increases service and product quality through improved operation of machinery and superior service of international service networks.

Increase of customer satisfaction (Business cases #2, #3, #4, #5, #6, #10)

Training, application service, error diagnosis and the identification of spare parts are major value propositions for OEMs to their customers. More efficient and effective management of the technicians leads to an increase of customer satisfaction. With the help of mobile collaborative AR systems, previously neglected distant customers may enjoy similar service levels as domestic customers. “[...] *When customers buy new systems, they always ask how we can support them. And if I have to say, 'of course you can call the hotline support in Germany [...]', the Vietnamese certainly says 'nice offer, but you are not available during my operating hours'. Therefore, we certainly benefit from qualifying service partners. Because it increases customer loyalty, if our systems can be serviced properly.*” Thus, customer satisfaction will increase.

Remarkably, we found only one OEM (use case #2, table 2) promoting lower total cost of ownership (TCO) to the customer. Neither in the focus group discussions, nor in the interviews did we observed this enabler.

3.2. Barriers

Connectivity (Business cases #1, #2, #7, #8, table 3)

Maintenance service usually takes place in the field or at the customer's production site. However, customers are often reluctant to open their Wi-Fi networks for external devices. Moreover, production sites may be situated in rural regions with poor bandwidth of wireless data connectivity. *"A problem that we definitely do have with the glasses is mobile connectivity, since our machinery is often located in some factory in the back of beyond. [...] Mobile reception is already bad outside at the car park and when you enter the building, then it becomes even worse."* Bottecchina et al. (2010) found that under experimental conditions experts preferred video resolution of at least 640x480 [12], which might not always be possible. Thus, connectivity is a major barrier to mobile collaborative AR field service.

Privacy protection (All ten business cases)

A major advantage of mobile collaborative AR systems is the possibility of storing screenshots and videos of maintenance or training sessions. However, the documentation function of the system is a barrier with respect to privacy concerns. Data security representatives and trade unions often insist that consent of all recorded participants is required. Although privacy protection is more likely to be an issue of LEs, rather than for SMEs, privacy concerns can also be a barrier from the personal perspective of technicians. The feeling of being monitored could become an issue.

Protection of intellectual property (Business cases #1, #2, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9)

Many companies within our sample serve customers that are rigorous in protecting their intellectual property. Interviewees assume, that technicians wearing HMDs might be banned from working at customer's production sites. As a participant puts it: *"We are forced to hand over our smartphone when we enter [...] and now we should convince them to walk in wearing glasses that feature a camera system with a video store function."* However, it was also stressed that when it comes to machine breakdowns, customers usually leave all concern behind since unavailability of production facilities is a much larger concern. *"Even the automotive industry gets this idea, [...] either your production is down for four hours or a day until my technician is there, or there is someone wearing glasses and your production continues [...]."*

Resistance of technicians (All ten business cases)

As with every new technology getting people to use HMDs might be a challenge. The reason for the resistance can be diverse, ranging from fashionable appearance to privacy concerns [28]. Besides, even if the benefits of the system are apparent from the business perspective, the personal perspective of technicians might be different. *"[...] experienced technicians often diagnose problems in a hands-on process. Some just don't see the advantages [of the technology] and therefore are reluctant. These older service guys are used to their tool kit and some even have problems in using a smartphone."*

Loss of service orders (Business case #3, #4, #5, #9, #10)

Deploying service technicians is an important source of revenue for many companies [29]. Equipping customers with HMDs poses the risk of losing field service orders, by training customer's personnel with every remote maintenance session. Mourtzis et al. (2017) outline a maintenance case of a robotics SME that illustrates this risk. In their case, a battery replacement is described to be crucial for securing the robots function, and usually requires the OEM to deploy a technician to the customer's site, although the task only requires simple assembly actions and could easily be explained remotely [15]. With this procedure the OEM qualifies the personnel of the customer. This qualification could lead to decreased service revenues, when customers execute simple tasks on their own. Obviously, this barrier is contrary to the aforementioned *ensure ability to respond* enabler.

Business model innovation (All ten business cases)

With respect to innovation enabled by the industrial internet of things, SMEs are typically challenged by their lack of resources, management know-how, selection of suitable solutions and the lack of transparency of the value of technologies [30]. Against those findings, the "transparency of value" does not seem to be a barrier concerning the use of mobile collaborative AR systems. All companies within our sample formulated the value of the technology

quite clearly. Consequently, a consensus was found in one focus group discussion that companies must be prepared with a smart service business model for the after-warranty period to monetize the improvements in service quality. However, as Kowalkowski et al. (2013) indicate, SMEs have more difficulties than larger companies to charge for service at all, as their revenue models are often based on product unit sales and large customers expect services for free [9]. Thus, using mobile collaborative AR systems might be an opportunity to innovate the business model and apply a more service-orientated strategy. Managers do not seem to have worked out such business models.

4. CONCLUSION

With the description of concrete business cases, enablers and barriers for AR supported service delivery, we contribute to the scarce research of servitization from the perspective of SMEs.

Our investigation indicates that use of mobile collaborative AR systems is an opportunity for SMEs to improve their service quality and extend their service businesses. New business opportunities arise, when providing mobile collaborative AR systems to service partners, sub-contractors and customers. The reduction of time that adds value (e.g. traveling time, lengthy error diagnostics, unnecessary technician deployment) and frees capacity to perform additional service orders subsequently might increase service revenues. The technology also facilitates international consistent quality of service to distant customers, which is a major challenge for SMEs. For SMEs who are generally more dependent on external service partners to provide customer support, mobile collaborative AR systems are an opportunity to expand their service business. Notably, no interviewee took the customers' perspective and considered the decreased total cost of ownership. Decreasing total cost of ownership might lead to higher sales of new equipment.

However, we were able to identify barriers to be addressed. Connectivity problems might be removed in the near future with the introduction of 5G networks. Barriers regarding protection of individual's privacy and company's intellectual property might be solved with further technology developments and/or contractual negotiation. Reluctance of human beings might disappear once the technology becomes more widespread. As of now, the loss of service orders and with it the lack of new business models to monetize the innovation is an unsolved issue.

Unlike the study by BMWi (2015) [30] suggests, we could not confirm the lack of transparency of the value barrier for mobile collaborative AR systems.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

The research strategy and data collection method are not without limitations. Especially external validity and transferability are issues when using a qualitative research approach. All results and conclusions are derived from information that relies on views from a limited number of individuals, stemming from a limited number of companies. The companies and interviewees were selected to ensure the validity of this study. However, to describe the investigated phenomena more precisely and confirm validity of the results, a larger number of companies should be included in our study. As more and more companies are implementing mobile collaborative AR systems, the outcome of this investigation should be tested in a quantitative large sample study. Furthermore, the economic value of the ten identified business cases should be assessed. A better understanding of barriers and enablers of mobile collaborative AR systems in field service is indispensable for developing robust business models for SMEs. From the perspective of servitization research it would be interesting to investigate whether or not AR is an enabler for SME servitization.

REFERENCES

- [1] VanDerMerwe S, Rada JF (1988) Servitization of business: Adding value by adding services. *European Management Journal* 6(4).
- [2] Martin CR, Horne DA (1992) Restructuring towards a Service Orientation: The Strategic Challenges. *International Journal of Service Industry Management* 3(1):25–38.
- [3] Wise R, Baumgartner P (September/Oktober Issue 1999) Go downstream: The new profit imperative in manufacturing. *Harvard Business Review* 77(5):133–41.
- [4] Mathieu V (2001) Product services: From a service supporting the product to a service supporting the client. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing* 16(1):39–61.
- [5] Davies A, Brady T, Hobday M (2006) Charting a path toward integrated solutions. *MIT Sloan Management Review* 47(3).

- [6] Lay G, Copani G, Jäger A, Biege S (2010) The relevance of service in European manufacturing industries. *Journal of Service Management* 21(5):715–26.
- [7] Aromaa S, Väättäen A, Aaltonen I, Heimonen T (2015) A model for gathering and sharing knowledge in maintenance work. *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Conference of the European Association of Cognitive Ergonomics*, pp. 1–8.
- [8] Storey DJ, Greene FJ (2010) *Small business and entrepreneurship*. Financial Times Prentice Hall, Harlow.
- [9] Kowalkowski C, Witell L, Gustafsson A (2013) Any way goes: Identifying value constellations for service infusion in SMEs. *Industrial Marketing Management* 42(1):18–30.
- [10] The Federal Statistic Office. *Destatis Datenbank. Beschäftigte und Umsatz der Betriebe im verarbeitenden Gewerbe: Deutschland, Jahre, Beschäftigtengrößenklassen (Wirtschaftszweige WZ2008 2-4-Steller Hierarchie) [Employees and Sales of German manufacturing companies of industry sector WZ2008]*.
- [11] Alem L, Tecchia F, Huang W (2011) Remote Tele-assistance System for Maintenance Operators in Mines. *11th Underground Coal Operators' Conference, University of Wollongong & the Australasian Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*:171–7.
- [12] Bottecchia S, Cieutat J-M, Jessel J-P (2010) T.A.C: Augmented Reality System for Collaborative Tele-Assistance in the Field of Maintenance through Internet. *Proceedings of the 1st Augmented Human International Conference*, Article No. 14.
- [13] Kraut RE, Miller MD, Siegel J (1996) Collaboration in Performance of Physical Tasks: Effects on Outcomes and Communication. *Proceedings of the 1996 ACM conference on Computer supported cooperative work*:57–66.
- [14] Plutz M, Große Böckmann M, Siebenkotten P, Schmitt R (2016) *Smart Glasses in der Produktion [smart glasses in manufacturing]: Studienbericht des Fraunhofer-Instituts für Produktionstechnologie IPT [Survey report of the Fraunhofer Institute for Production Technology]*. Fraunhofer IPT, Aachen.
- [15] Mourtzis D, Zogopoulos V, Vlachou E (2017) Augmented Reality Application to Support Remote Maintenance as a Service in the Robotics Industry. *Procedia CIRP* 63:46–51.
- [16] Sutherland IE (1965) The Ultimate Display. *Proceedings of IFIP Congress*:506–8.
- [17] Quint F, Loch F, Bertram P (2017) The Challenge of Introducing AR in Industry - Results of a Participative Process Involving Maintenance Engineers. *Procedia Manufacturing* 11:1319–23.
- [18] Palmarini R, Erkoyuncu JA, Roy R, Torabmostaedi H (2018) A systematic review of augmented reality applications in maintenance. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 49:215–28.
- [19] Kurata T, Sakata N, Kourogi M, Kuzuoka H, Billingham M (2004) Remote Collaboration using a Shoulder-Worn Active Camera/Laser. *ISWC 2004: Eighth International Symposium on Wearable Computers proceedings 31 October-3 November, 2004, Arlington, Virginia*. IEEE Computer Society. Los Alamitos, Calif, pp. 62–69.
- [20] Zhong XW, Boulanger P, Georganas ND (2002) Collaborative Augmented Reality: A Prototype for Industrial Training. *21th Biennial Symposium on Communication, Canada*.
- [21] Alem L, Huang W (2011) Developing Mobile Remote Collaboration Systems for Industrial Use: Some Design Challenges. in Campos P, Graham N, Jorge J, Nunes N, Palanque P, Winckler M, (Eds.). *Human-computer interaction - INTERACT 2011: 13th IFIP TC 13 international conference, Lisbon, Portugal, September 5 - 9, 2011 ; proceedings, part IV*. Springer. Berlin, pp. 442–445.
- [22] Huck-Fries V, Wiegand F, Klinker K, Wiesche M, Krcmar H (2017) Datenbrillen in der Wartung [smart glasses in maintenance]. in Eibl M, Gaedke M, (Eds.). *Informatik 2017 - Bände I-III: Tagung vom 25.-29. September 2017 in Chemnitz*. Gesellschaft für Informatik. Bonn.
- [23] Miles MB, Huberman AM (1994) *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. 2nd ed. Sage, Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- [24] Günterberg B (2012) *Unternehmensgrößenstatistik [company size statistics]: Unternehmen, Umsatz und sozialversicherungspflichtige Beschäftigte 2004 bis 2009 in Deutschland*. Ergebnisse des Unternehmensregisters (URS 95), Bonn.
- [25] Miles MB, Huberman AM, Saldaña J (2014) *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook*. 3rd ed. Sage, Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore, Washington DC.
- [26] Fussell, Susan R., Setlock, Leslie D., Kraut, Robert E. (2003) Effects of Head-Mounted and Scene-Oriented Video Systems on Remote Collaboration on Physical Tasks. *New horizons conference proceedings, Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* 5(1):513–20.
- [27] Gebauer H, Paiola M, Edvardsson B (2010) Service business development in small and medium capital goods manufacturing companies. *Managing Service Quality* 20(2):123–39.
- [28] van Krevelen DWF, Poelman R (2010) Survey of Augmented Reality Technologies, Applications and Limitations. *The International Journal of Virtual Reality* 9(2):1–20.
- [29] VDMA (2016) *VDMA-Benchmarks Kundendienst 2016 [customer service benchmarking survey]*, Frankfurt.
- [30] BMWi (2015) *Industrie 4.0 - Volks- und betriebswirtschaftliche Faktoren für den Standort Deutschland [Study on macroeconomic and microeconomic factors in the context of Industry 4.0 in Germany]: Eine Studie im Rahmen der Begleitforschung zum Technologieprogramm AUTONOMIK für Industrie 4.0*, Berlin.